

D2.1 – Dissemination & Exploitation plan report

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Scholarly Communication Services for EOSC users

D2.1 – Dissemination & Exploitation plan report

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This deliverable describes the overall communication strategy of the OpenAIRE Nexus to i) reach maximum exposure of OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio, ii) engage with EOSC users and foster collaboration with INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 projects.

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Acronym	Description
ARC	Athena Research and Innovation Center
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUDAT	European Collaborative Data Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HELIX	Hellenic Data Service
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NCPs	National Contact Points
NOADs	National Open Access Desk
OSC	Open Science Corner
RDA	Research Data Alliance
S.M.A.R.T.	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, Timely
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SME	Small and Medium sized Enterprise
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
VPC	Value proposition canvas

Publishable Summary

THE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY OF OPENAIRE NEXUS

This deliverable describes the overall communication strategy of the OpenAIRE-Nexus project, along with the dissemination activities and exploitation plan, with the aim of:

- i. maximising exposure of OpenAIRE-Nexus' portfolio of services in a quantitative (KPIs) and qualitative way,
- ii. engaging with EOSC users and fostering collaboration with INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 projects.

The communication strategy aims to achieve the OpenAIRE-Nexus communication and project objectives. The major components of this strategy presented in the next sections are identified per OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio service and are based on:

- Project communication goals.
- Service paths towards sustainability and innovation.
- Project communication plan.
- Communication and dissemination channels.
- Exploitation plan.

Information from previous experiences and lessons learnt from past OpenAIRE projects and current INFRAEOSC-03, INFRAEOSC-07 projects are also considered.

The report is structured to follow the methodology used to describe the value proposition of the OpenAIRE services portfolios, and based on a well-defined business and brand strategy used by entrepreneurship schools -SMART (S.M.A.R.T - Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, Timely) objectives and metrics -and communicate the messages to OpenAIRE users and the Open Science community.

After the initial analysis of the portfolio services, the report focuses on the potential exploitation techniques that can drive the OpenAIRE portfolio services uptake.

1 INTRODUCTION

Writing a deliverable focusing on a living organism like the OpenAIRE-Nexus project, with users and services interacting, growing, and evolving at the same time, is a challenge. Therefore, a methodological approach should primarily be considered.

There are four main considerations:

- The need for a more holistic approach to communicate how the services fit into the EOSC ecosystem and offer solutions to EOSC users along with the other INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 projects.
- To plan the communication strategy in agreement with the D3.1-Roadmap to semantic and technical interoperability (month 2 of the project), D3.2-Roadmap to deliver uniform packaging of OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio (month 3 of the project). If necessary, any alignments should be considered after the latest D3.3-Roadmap to semantic and technical interoperability (month 14 of the project).
- To consult the OpenAIRE-Nexus Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) monitored throughout the project duration and beyond.
- To apply the latest modernized approaches to describe OpenAIRE-Nexus services, their value, and characteristics.

All the information above leads to the exploitation plan drawn based on previous experiences, lessons learnt, new approaches, and ideas that can be realistically applied to OpenAIRE-Nexus within EOSC. As stated in the Grant Agreement, this report also presents a detailed plan of the engagement activities of OpenAIRE-Nexus, based on specific engagement strategy principles.

After all, the OpenAIRE-Nexus mission as stated in DOA; *is to offer a suite of services which bring scholarly communication in the centre of EOSC, allowing researchers, infrastructure providers, policy makers, businesses, and citizens to easily perform open science (buy in), to co-develop services and processes (make it user-centric) and to innovate (add value).*

2 METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methodologies and tools that were used to shape this report. The first one is borrowed from tech startups and is the Value Proposition Canvas, while the second is used in marketing and is the S.M.A.R.T. approach. A detailed description of both methodologies follows in the next two subsections.

2.1 The Value Proposition Canvas

We start by analyzing the value propositions of each of the portfolio services based on the template of Peter J. Thomson¹, which is an improved version of the famous Alexander Osterwalder version of the value proposition canvas (VPC), introduced back in 2012. The two major additions of the Thomson version take into consideration marketing, branding, persuasion techniques and behavioral psychology or customer behavior research. In other words, this is behavioral economics and choice psychology.

Why do we need the Value Proposition Canvas (VPC)?²

- **Better customer understanding:** the fact that you begin by analyzing your customer is powerful because it makes our approach more customer-centric. It urges the services providers (OpenAIRE) to view the user's point of view.
- **Focus and service development direction:** it is a benchmark to measure the urgency of new features and service improvements, moving in the right direction.
- **Messaging improvements:** finding the right message to attract new customers by building the VPC is a way to approach users and what we need to promise them.

¹ <https://www.peterjthomson.com/2013/11/value-proposition-canvas/>

² <https://valchanova.me/value-proposition-canvas-template-guide/>

Value Proposition Canvas

Based on the work of Steve Blank, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Yves Pigneur and Alex Osterwalder. Released under creative commons license to encourage adaption and iteration. No rights asserted.

FIGURE 1. THE IMPROVED VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Figure 1 shows the main questions we need to answer for each OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio service: What the customer (user) Fears, Needs, Wants, and if not using our services; What is the solution or service they use instead? We follow this by describing the Experience we promise to our users, and the Benefits and Features they get through our services.

At the centre of the circle in Figure 1 is the user that has the following feelings:

- **Wants** – the *emotional* drivers of decision-making are things that we want to **be, do or have**, and are powerful motivators of action. For example, I **want** to share the knowledge along with my domain expertise and **feel** prestigious and proud of my work.
- **Needs** – the user needs are the *rational* things that he/she needs to get done. Interestingly, needs are not always conscious because users might not know about them yet. The needs speak more to the pull of our heads and rational motivations.

A typical example are the massive groups of supporters of open source operating systems and software like Linux, Apache, MongoDB, because they want to be able to view the source code and support any developments needed. It's a matter of philosophy in life, not just a computer software approach.

- **Fears** – these can drive users' actions or inertia. Fears can be a strong driver of purchasing behavior and can be the hidden source of wants and needs. Customer fears are often the secret reason for using or buying a service. A typical example is a user who does his/her work by using a specific service and has a secret “**pain of switching**” when deciding to use a competitive service. For example, even if OpenAIRE provides a much better service, persuading a user to overcome the inertia of the status quo is difficult.
- **Substitutes** – the substitutes on the canvas are not just the obvious competitors but also include the existing **behaviors and coping mechanisms**. For example, the OpenAIRE Amnesia service performs data anonymization, which is fundamental when managing sensitive data. Amnesia helps researchers to comply with legislative data protections, including GDPR, with the final aim to be ‘open as possible, and **closed** as necessary’. Without Amnesia, researchers had to anonymize data either manually, asking legislation experts, or creating their own scripts or algorithms.

Meanwhile, the left side of Figure 1 focuses on the service side. It describes the widely accepted marketing terms of features and benefits with the addition of the experience. The elements of the service to consider are:

- **Features** – these are functioning **attributes** of the services, **how** they satisfy users' needs.
- **Benefits** – the ways that features make our customer's life easier by increasing **pleasure** or decreasing **pain (what)**. The benefits of the services are the core of their value proposition.
- **Experience** – the product experience is the way that using the OpenAIRE services makes the customer **feel**. It is the total of the combined features and benefits. It is more about the emotional reasons **why** people buy/use our services and what it means for them in their own lives. The product experience is the kernel that will help identify the market positioning and brand essence that is usually built out of the value proposition.

To summarize, it is important to clearly describe the VPC of the OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio services. Once this is completed, it is easier to describe what shall be communicated, why and how, to whom and when, by using the S.M.A.R.T methodology that follows.

2.2 S.M.A.R.T- Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, Timely

S.M.A.R.T methodology is about shaping the goals of OpenAIRE-Nexus communication and setting an action plan over time. There are five steps identified for OpenAIRE-Nexus services.

FIGURE 2. THE S.M.A.R.T METHODOLOGY APPLIED ON OPENAIRE-NEXUS

2.2.1 Step 1 - Market analysis

It is important to understand and position the OpenAIRE-Nexus services on the big Open Science ecosystem market and beyond. This is possible by examining the stakeholders of OpenAIRE-Nexus and the market dynamics through a SWOT and competitive analysis.

2.2.1.1 STAKEHOLDER'S MAPPING

To begin, we need to perform a stakeholder's mapping and recognize who the users of the services are. This is done for all OpenAIRE-Nexus services and is depicted in the Value Proposition Canvas designed for each one of the services.

The Stakeholder's matrix for all services is underway. An example for ARGOS is presented below.

TABLE 1. ARGOS STAKEHOLDERS' MATRIX EXAMPLE

ARGOS stakeholders' Matrix example						
	Category	Stakeholder	Influence	Interest	Support	Comments

1	Internal	OpenAIRE communications team	High	High	High	
2	Internal	NOADs	High	High	High	
3	Internal	Amnesia	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Applies for any related service of OpenAIRE
4	Internal	Working group	High	High	High	
5	Internal	Technical OpenAIRE team	High	Moderate	High	
6	Internal	Developing team	Low	Moderate	High	
7	Internal	Product Manager	High	High	High	
8	External	EOSC	High	High	Moderate	e-Infrastructure
9	External	Funders	High	High	High	
10	External	Policy makers	High	Low	Low	
11	External	Research facilitators, NCPs, EU liaison offices	High	High	Moderate	
12	External	UN	Moderate	Low	Low	
13	External	EUDAT	High	High	High	e-Infrastructure
14	External	RDA group on common standards DMP	High	High	Moderate	
15	External	HELIX	Moderate	High	High	The same applies to all

						national research repositories.
16	External	Copernicus	High	Low	Low	
17	External	SMEs with R&D i.e. Samsung, Huawei, Pharmas	High	Moderate	Low	
18	External	(Scientific) Journals Publishers	High	High	High	Mostly for open science journals
19	External	Research Communities	High	High	Moderate	
20	External	Press/Media	High	Low	Low	
21	External	Individuals that are top influencers	High	High	Probable High	Simms is a top Influencer, his paper initiated the RDA group
22	External	Tool providers	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Depends on the organizations policies
23	External	Infrastructure operators	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	
24	External	Repository staff and managers	Moderate	High	High	
25	External	Software developers	High	Moderate	Moderate	
26	External	Librarians	High	High	High	
27	External	W3C	Moderate	Moderate	Low	

28	External	Force 11 FAIR DMP	Low	Moderate	Low	DMP Fora in general
29	External	Belmont Forum e-infrastructures	Low	Moderate	Low	
30	External & Internal	Volunteers	Moderate	High	Moderate	
31	External	NGOs	Low	Moderate	Low	
32	Internal & External	OpenAIRE NaMeCo (National Membership Consortia)	Moderate	High	Moderate	NaMeCo is in progress
33	External	Data stewards/experts	High	High	Moderate	

2.2.1.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Following the stakeholder’s mapping, a SWOT analysis is needed to spot the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of a service. All OpenAIRE-Nexus services are in the process of defining a SWOT analysis. An example for ARGOS is shown in the following table.

TABLE 2. ARGOS SWOT ANALYSIS EXAMPLE

ARGOS SWOT Analysis example	
Internal Factors	
STRENGTHS (+)	WEAKNESSES (-)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality and durability ensured • Turns data into FAIR data by design • Links to trusted sources • Configures to community's needs • Detailed How-to guide • Positive impact to society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grows in relation to communities and users knowledge on DMPs • Is affected from any delays from external resources •

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be white-labeled • Allows collaborative writing (invite contributors) • Flexible - enables creation of user-selected templates • Can be combined with OpenAIRE Amnesia to ensure that sensitive data plans that contain information about i.e., medical records are properly handled • Connected to Open Science Monitor 	
<p>External Factors</p>	
<p>OPPORTUNITIES (+)</p>	<p>THREATS (-)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive to all researchers and research coordinators • Used by Funding and Research Performing Organizations • Research communities may use the tool and create Dataset Description templates • May be used for purposes other than research projects (e.g., training) • Positive impact to society • Promotes Open Science • Collaboration & association with other well-established platforms/tools. • Can be standardised by Funders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The “Dataset description” is introduced, which may lead to low acceptability by the community due to non-familiarity • Is related as a service tool, closely to OpenAIRE budget and funds • Same applies with EU funds • Commercial DMPs may get a significant market percentage • Competition is growing fast and developing rapidly • DMP online is very well established and is dominant in the sector • High institutional reputational risk if the DMP is not available in ARGOS • Verification and integrity of research (and data) should be promoted

2.2.1.3 COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS

Being part of the active and growing Open Science ecosystem means that there is also competition for services. It is crucial to know who the competitors are for a service and how they develop. An example follows for ARGOS.

TABLE 3. ARGOS COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS EXAMPLE

ARGOS Competitive Analysis example		
Category	Strength	Details
Internal (Strengths)	Data quality and durability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identifies actions to ensure quality and durability for data ● Enriches the OpenAIRE research Graph. Connected to OpenAIRE underlying services, e.g., Zenodo for publishing DMPs and assigning DOIs ● Adds to compliance measures of the OpenAIRE Monitoring service ● Supports collaborative writing and versioning of DMPs ● Supports RDA metadata standards, making ARGOS machine-actionable; interoperable, with automatic exchange, integration and validation of information provided (PID checks to link to an existing dataset, etc ● Integrates Zenodo ● Infrastructure providers automate processes via universal formats and standards (metadata)
Internal	FAIR data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Turns data into FAIR data by design ● Supports exports in JSON format; DMPs can be exported by ARGOS and imported for use in other DMP tools, and vice versa ● Free, unlimited storage, automatic back-up, secure, easy access of DMPs ● Supports export of machine-readable files; JSON, XML, PDF, DOC
Internal	Links to trusted sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● It is the joint effort of OpenAIRE and EUDAT CDI. Linking DMPs with research artifacts they correspond to, thus enabling validation processes to be performed. ● Automatic validation of information among funders, repositories, researchers, organizations ● Help to build trust and confidence among researchers because of a higher granularity of available information

Internal	Configures to community's needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addresses FAIR and Open best practices and assumes no barriers for its use and adoption Accompanies researchers work even after graduation, even if there is a career switch Can be fully integrated into systems and workflows of the wider research data management environment ARGOS modular design allows customizations and extensions
Internal	Detailed How-to guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> www.openaire.eu/argos-guide
Internal	Positive reflection to society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the public investments are well distributed/handled
External (Opportunities)	Inclusive to all researchers and research coordinators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ARGOS is developed in accordance with global standards for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (DMPs), as they are derived by the RDA DMP Common Standards Working Group
External	Funding and Research Performing Organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ARGOS can be configured by institutions, research communities and funders in order to meet their specific requirements
External	Research communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be used by researchers, research coordinators and students who are required to write DMPs Promotes interdisciplinary research and assists researchers to find, validate and re-use data
External	Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be used by researchers, research coordinators and students who would like to familiarize themselves with the process of writing DMPs. Can be used to train in classroom future researchers and professionals as part of research data management course

External	Positive impact on society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can inform citizens of the importance of data and how knowledge is accumulated through scientific research. • Can be used by internal organizations (mostly public ones) that cannot afford to spend money on DMP. Hospitals can be a great case. • ARGOS can assist UN goals i.e., on observational measurements on climate, where there are unique and extremely important data points that cannot be reproduced
External	Promotes Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can utilize the data and information in OpenAIRE and promote Open Science • Can be an add-on tool to Open Science in Europe and EOSC
External	Collaboration & Association with other well-established platforms/tools/services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It collaborates with RDA machine-actionable DMPs interest group • Copernicus data are a huge amount of information and would be important to manage them, ARGOS should be a must-use tool • Can be associated with HELIX and for example lead and train ARC, and other research orgs how to create their own personalized DMPs. • Connect with re3data.org to add value to repositories, i.e., DOI • When GDPR applies, or there are sensitive medical data, the OpenAIRE service Amnesia can be used to anonymize the data and then allow users to link to them in their DMP • Can be connected to FAIRSharing.org

2.2.2 Step 2 - Messages

2.2.2.1 CUSTOMIZED PER USER

All messages necessarily sound clear and comprehensive to all users. The messages to communicate the same service differs from user “A” with needs “X” and user “B” with needs “Y”.

2.2.2.2 GROUP (EOSC) OR LOCATION SPECIFIC

EOSC users and related stakeholders are interested to know information regarding the OpenAIRE-Nexus services and EOSC, and how these services change and add value to the outcome of their work. Like users in different continents, they are driven by different motives and understand a message when it's expressed in a way they are familiar with.

2.2.2.3 CUSTOMIZED BASED ON USER EXPERIENCE

Messages also differ when the target user is a new one, who needs more information than a user who already has experience using the specific or similar service and is already familiar with certain acronyms, processes, jargon, and any other technicalities. An indication of user groups based on experience follows:

- Beginner in knowledge: never heard about the service offer (i.e: never heard about DMP).
- Beginner in performs: People may know what a service is offering, but they may not know how to use it
- Intermediate: know/how to do, but not fully confident with it
- Advanced: know/how use the service and confident and enthusiast with that

2.2.2.4 CUSTOMIZED BASED ON NEW VS EXPERIENCED USER GROUP

Messages to a user who is onboarding differ from messages to experienced users. The latter enter the communication and engagement process from a later stage.

2.2.3 Step 3 - Design Material

2.2.3.1 SERVICE BRANDING

OpenAIRE-Nexus services should be easily recognizable by the users. Their logos and OpenAIRE brand should be easily identifiable and visible; the key messages of OpenAIRE-Nexus should support the brand and the value proposition of the service; the positioning of the brand in the Open Science ecosystem and among competitors should be evident; the brand voice (copywriting, websites) needs to be clear; a style guide among OpenAIRE and OpenAIRE-Nexus services should be similar; and of course, social media strategy should align with the OpenAIRE brand identity in a more playful manner balancing brand messaging, voice and values with the style and focus of the social media tool³ used.

2.2.3.2 SERVICE USEFUL MATERIAL

Any possible form of useful material that will make users satisfied should be provided. There is plenty of flexibility and options for experimentation, to understand which users are engaged via which form (i.e. a video, a demo, a leaflet, a 1-1 call, a questionnaire, etc.).

³ <https://www.brafton.com/blog/strategy/branding-services/>

2.2.3.3 SERVICE SUPPORTIVE MATERIAL

All OpenAIRE-Nexus services must be accompanied with supportive material for users. Starting with tutorials and user guides, to explanatory videos and digital printouts.

2.2.4 Step 4 - Tools & Tactics

2.2.4.1 DIGITAL MARKETING

Since all OpenAIRE-Nexus services are digital, accessible via virtual environments, digital marketing is a necessity to promote them. Usually, digital marketing refers to forms, online videos, social media posts, quizzes, email campaigns, SEO, etc.⁴. Digital marketing also offers live-measurement of quantifiable results, adjustments, and personalization. Above all, it provides a step-by-step analysis of user actions through defined and measurable predefined user funnels.

2.2.4.2 PUBLIC ROADMAP

This refers to the open and transparent way of sharing future plans for OpenAIRE-Nexus services. Public Roadmaps should be used wisely since they have upsides and downsides⁵. On one hand, OpenAIRE Public Roadmaps build trust with other actors in the Open Science ecosystem, evolving users in the development process, while on the other hand, sharing the roadmaps may expose information to competitors or disappoint users for not delivering on time or creating higher expectations than the one delivered.

2.2.4.3 USER FEEDBACK

Collecting user feedback is a vital part of the service-making and evolving process. It consists of information regarding user satisfaction (i.e. via surveys, forums). Feedback has an additional role to help OpenAIRE understand how and if the users of the services recognise the OpenAIRE-Nexus brand and link it or confuse it with the OpenAIRE brand.

On public events, OpenAIRE-Nexus is using [Mentimeter](#) to create an interactive environment with live Q&As, polls, and quizzes with the audience and collect instant feedback and user requirements.

2.2.4.4 OPEN SCIENCE CORNER

The Open Science Corner (OSC) first appeared through the OpenAIRE-Nexus project, and its vision is to establish a hands-on experience website for OpenAIRE-Nexus and EOSC users (new and current). In particular, the OSC will enable users to perform Open Science in the full research lifecycle by using OpenAIRE-Nexus services, open scholarly publications, software, and datasets. Therefore, users will cross the line from being potential users to actual users, gaining

⁴ <https://mailchimp.com/marketing-glossary/digital-marketing/>

⁵ <https://productcoalition.com/public-product-roadmap-yes-please-7303ed2db21e>

confidence by actual experience and skills that are gradually built via OSC. We aim to target ‘innovators’ defined as users enthusiastic to try new technologies, ‘early adopters’ who are not familiar with new technologies but willing to try, and ‘early majority’ who are those driven to use new technologies for practical reason (i.e reducing time in writing a DMP for a funder deliverable, in the case of Argos)⁶(Figure 4).

The OSC will cover the full research lifecycle (Figure 3), through its four portfolio services: PUBLISH, TRACK (previous MONITOR), DISCOVER, and EXPAND.

FIGURE 3. SOURCE: LYON, LIZ. (2016). *TRANSPARENCY: THE EMERGING THIRD DIMENSION OF OPEN SCIENCE AND OPEN DATA. LIBER QUARTERLY. 25. 153. 10.18352/LQ.10113.*

It should be noted here that there are five user groups in the technology/service adoption lifecycle, classified in 1962 by the sociologist Everett Rogers in the book ‘Diffusion of Innovations’⁷, where each group has a different buying habit. The key action is to succeed in helping users to cross the chasm, otherwise the service in our case will be deprecated.

⁶ <https://www.business-to-you.com/crossing-the-chasm-technology-adoption-life-cycle/>

⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/gp/product/0743222091/>

FIGURE 4. THE USER GROUPS IN RELATION THE THE INNOVATION DIFFUSION

OpenAIRE-Nexus through the forthcoming EOSC-DIH ⁸(Digital Innovation Hub) and the overall OpenAIRE A.M.K.E. communication strategy will continue to focus on the communication, dissemination, and engagement of new and current services by:

- attracting innovators and embracing new services early adopters and help them overcome any chasm
- continuing the supporting and training activities and enriching them with additional ones
- enhancing the current and exploring new interconnected communication channels (i.e. the updated OpenAIRE catalogue, Open Science Corner, Podcasts, and more)
- re-defining the OpenAIRE-Nexus services messages so that all users can easily comprehend their value
- updating and modernizing the OpenAIRE catalogue to present the value of OpenAIRE services and Open Science services of EOSC to all stakeholders, along with a more user-centric presentation

The Open Science corner is a hands-on experience corner designed to present the full research lifecycle to all OpenAIRE portal visitors by combining already established supporting material,

⁸ <https://eosc-dih.eu/>

practices, and methods along with the latest SMEs applications provided by the OpenAIRE-Advance H2020 project (GA: 777541). The goal is for users to build experience, confidence, and skills necessary for Open Science services with a focus on EOSC. This process lowers any barriers for users and, at the same time, works as a feedback loop for INFRAEOSC-03 services creators. The vision is that multiple domains and different users would find the information they need to provide, enrich, and explore data and services, view statistics and graphs (impact trends, activity monitoring) before using the OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio services. Best practices could be focused not only on researchers but also on funders and policymakers to 'run' simulation scenarios and experience firsthand how the living EOSC ecosystem works and its outcomes.

2.2.4.5 ANALYTICS

An open-source analytic platform called '[Matomo](#)' is used to monitor the analytics related to all OpenAIRE-Nexus services websites. An overview of the page with the information is shown in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5. AN EXAMPLE OF THE MATOMO DASHBOARD

Some of the parameters monitored are:

- Websites' traffic
- Unique and total visitors
- Visits overview
- Location of visitors

- Users acquisition from various channels (social media, websites, search engines, campaigns)

2.2.5 Step 5 - Communication channels

2.2.5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA

The social media accounts that OpenAIRE-Nexus is using are the same as those since the inception of OpenAIRE as a project. That means, there is already an active user community that supports Open Science and wishes to get informed on the OpenAIRE-Nexus services through:

TABLE 4. SOCIAL MEDIA

Twitter		@openaire_eu	

<p>LinkedIn Group⁹</p>	<p>Ideal for users' inquiries, discussions</p>	
<p>LinkedIn OpenAIRE AMKE Company page¹⁰</p>	<p>Ideal for dissemination of events, share news and more trackable information</p>	

⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3893548/>

¹⁰ https://www.linkedin.com/company/openaire-eu/?l=en_US

<p>Facebook Group¹¹</p>	<p>Open to a broader audience</p>	
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2.2.5.2 WORKSHOPS, EVENTS

TABLE 5. WORKSHOPS, EVENTS

<p>Community Calls¹²</p>	<p>Monthly calls are arranged around a topic and related services. Open to all users and the notes (Google Doc), slides (Zenodo) and recordings (YouTube) are available. Upcoming calls and agendas also are published beforehand.</p>
<p>Tech-clinics for NOADs (internal)</p>	<p>Internal focused on NOADs presentations and discussions around a service. An example of</p>

¹¹ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/openaire/>

¹² <https://www.openaire.eu/provide-community-calls>

	Episciences presentation is available on Zenodo here ¹³
EOSC Symposium 2021 ¹⁴	A dedicated EOSC event where OpenAIRE-Nexus services apply and communicate their value and latest news to the EOSC community. Presentation material is also publicly available here ¹⁵ . For a detailed list, please view the D2.2.
OSFAIR 2021 ¹⁶	Continuing to bring all Open Science stakeholders around a table to discuss, present and elaborate on interesting topics, OpenAIRE-Nexus services are presented via workshops, demos, presentations and discussions.
Open Repositories Conference 2021	OpenAIRE-Nexus service Zenodo, hosts the Open Repositories community ¹⁷ For OpenAIRE-Nexus participation please view D2.2
RDA plenaries ¹⁸	Throughout the years, OpenAIRE services were promoted via poster presentations, discussions, presentations, and focused working groups.
COAR Symposium	Information is available on D2.2.
OpenAIRE NOADs	All OpenAIRE NOADs perform regular or on-demand meetings with interested stakeholders and promote both the OpenAIRE-Nexus services and Open Science and EOSC in general.

2.2.5.3 SYNERGIES

TABLE 6. SYNERGIES

INFRAEOSC-03 ¹⁹	Blog articles, communication material (i.e., podcasts) and related activities are supported.
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¹³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4908971#.YSOZdo4zauc>

¹⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/events/eosc-symposium-2021>

¹⁵ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium-2021-programme>

¹⁶ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/openrepos/?page=1&size=20>

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries>

¹⁹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-03-2020

INFRAEOSC-07²⁰	Regularly scheduled meetings are set up to foster alignment of OpenAIRE-Nexus and all INFRAEOSC-07 projects on all levels. A dedicated section on "Paths for collaboration with short presentations of INFRAEOSC-07 projects" run and was publicly open during the OpenAIRE-Nexus public launch event ²¹ . The presentations and recordings are available to all on Zenodo ²² and YouTube ²³ . OpenAIRE-Nexus services are also promoted in the INFRAEOSC-07 public launch events.
EOSC-FUTURE²⁴	OpenAIRE-Nexus services are expected to be promoted via the upcoming EOSC-FUTURE Digital Innovation Hub ²⁵ where industry actors and SMEs would be called to create or enhance services based on EOSC ones.
EOSC-FUTURE and INFRAEOSC-07 projects	A joint uptake activity with a Memorandum of Understanding will be signed among OpenAIRE-Nexus and EOSC-Future, as part of the INFRAEOSC-07 projects.
R3data²⁶	OpenAIRE-Nexus is in close cooperation with re3data (Registry of Research Data Repositories) to discuss and elaborate on the latest common metadata schemas findings and improve all further OpenAIRE-Nexus services interoperability with EOSC-FUTURE services and INFRAEOSC-07 ones.
SCOSS²⁷ members²⁸	OpenAIRE AMKE members and partners participate in the SCOSS and maintain open communication and support.

2.2.5.4 EOSC CATALOGUE (MARKETPLACE)

²⁰ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_INFRAEOSC-07-2020

²¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-nexus-public-launch-event>

²² <https://zenodo.org/record/4597641>

²³ https://youtu.be/col-YU0_qYA

²⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101017536>

²⁵ <https://eosc-dih.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.re3data.org/>

²⁷ <https://scoss.org/>

²⁸ <https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/who-is-behind-scoss/>

There is an open and publicly available EOSC catalogue of all registered services on the EOSC marketplace²⁹. All OpenAIRE-Nexus services are available through a simple search and filter of all options³⁰ (see image below).

The screenshot displays the 'Resources' section of the EOSC marketplace. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Contact us', 'Portal Home', 'Catalogue & Marketplace', 'Providers Dashboard', and 'Login'. Below this is the 'EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD' logo and a search bar with the text 'Find resource...'. The search results are filtered by 'Providers: OpenAIRE'. The main content area shows a list of resources, including 'AMNESIA' (Anonymize your datasets), 'ARGOS' (Plan and follow your data), and 'Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage OpenAIRE Community Gateway'. Each resource card includes a description, the organization (OpenAIRE), and the scientific domain (Generic). The page also features a sidebar with 'All Resources' and 'Categories' (Access physical & infrastructures, Aggregators & Integrators, etc.) and a 'Filters' section for 'Scientific Domains'.

FIGURE 6. THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS SERVICES ON EOSC CATALOGUE (MARKETPLACE)

Since EOSC is using its own Provider Data model³¹ and Resource Data model³² for all EOSC services, all the OpenAIRE-Nexus services follow its example and provide at least the mandatory fields requested. This is a good dissemination channel for the OpenAIRE-Nexus services, where EOSC users can read the service description, the target users, TRL, find all supportive material, and access the service.

²⁹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

³⁰ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services?providers%5B%5D=70>

³¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-provider-profile>

³² <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-resource-profile>

2.2.5.5 THE OPENAIRE CATALOGUE

As of late August 2021, the OpenAIRE catalogue is available in a specific UI/UX formation, using the same EOSC model and comparative approach. Experience and user feedback showed that users need to see and understand in a friendly way the value of a service (how it solves their problems, the benefits, etc.) to encourage them to keep reading about it, continuing with features and enhancements. Therefore, a newly defined OpenAIRE catalogue model incorporates user needs and information from the previously explained VPCs and marketing goodies, combined with all the material of OpenAIRE (supportive, communicative, training). The new OpenAIRE catalogue, a modern take on the user-centric approach, is under development and is expected to be a new powerful online communication channel early October 2021. A detailed comparison follows below.

TABLE 7. HIGH LEVEL COMPARISON OF EOSC VS NEW OPENAIRE CATALOGUE

	User Centric Homepage	Service Centric Homepage	Plenty of Supportive Material	Rich Communication Material	Related Services	Marketing information	Financial information	KPIs
EOSC Catalogue	-	√	-	-	√	Min	Min	-
New OpenAIRE Catalogue	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

A more detailed comparison is below. Some examples are the newly introduced material to the OpenAIRE catalogue, and the re-grouping and definition of four main user groups and ten sub-users' groups.

TABLE 8. DETAILED COMPARISON OF EOSC VS NEW OPENAIRE CATALOGUE

	Benefits and Feature, Dynamic KPIs	Pitch Material & information	Inverted logo & Media Kit	Coding & Datasets material, Feedback, Roadmap	Community calls, Webinars, Workshops	Factsheets, Guides, Tutorials, Use cases Glossary	Podcast, Videos, MOOC,	Payment categories, Pricing information
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EOSC Catalogue	-	-	Only logo	-	Only one general	One	Multimedia	One payment model, one pricing
New OpenAIRE Catalogue	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

FIGURE 7. AN EXAMPLE OF THE NEW CATALOGUE MOCKS

FIGURE 8. AN EXAMPLE OF THE NEW CATALOGUE SERVICE OVERVIEW MOCKS

The vision is to use the new catalogue as an easy way for the user to preview OpenAIRE-Nexus services, with a main portal to learn and get informed of the services, follow updates, and engage. It is a single point of ‘selling’ for the services and a returning reference point.

2.2.5.6 OPENAIRE ESTABLISHED NETWORK & COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

TABLE 9. ESTABLISHED NETWORK & COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

NOADs³³	Through the NOADs network in many countries, OpenAIRE-Nexus, continuing from OpenAIRE-Advance project, disseminates Open Science events, promotes OpenAIRE-Nexus services, forms blog articles and news, presents the services to universities, institutions and organizations, provides support and engages users.
Blogs³⁴	OpenAIRE portal hosts blogs , to invite and inform users of OpenAIRE-Nexus services and other topics.
Newsletter (OpenAIRE AMKE)	A monthly newsletter rolls out for years through OpenAIRE. Continuing this action, OpenAIRE-Nexus provides to the monthly newsletter, content regarding the services.
Portal & Webpages	The OpenAIRE.eu portal supports OpenAIRE-Nexus and works as the primary dissemination and communication portal channel. All blog posts, articles, news and updates of the OpenAIRE-Nexus services pass through the portal.

2.3 Multi-experience approach

2.3.1 The Customer Journey Canvas method

³³ <https://www.openaire.eu/noad-activities>

³⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/categories/infrastructure>

To offer a multi-experience to OpenAIRE-Nexus users, the “Customer Journey Canvas”³⁵ model was used. This helps identify, improve, re-evaluate, and spot any gaps in the actions that a user has:

i. Before entering the service

This period includes the actions performed by the service provider via the communication channels like advertising/public relations, social media, word-of-mouth, past experiences.

ii. While entering the service

This period includes specific steps that the user follows when accessing the service (internal paths).

iii. After they leave the service

This is comparable to the after-sale period when the service provider has to manage customer relationships and attract new users via social media or word-of-mouth communication.

At the end of each step, the users’ expectations (before using the service), the user experiences (while using the services) and the user satisfaction/dissatisfaction opinions (after using the service) are noted.

³⁵ <https://thecanvasrevolution.com/product/customer-journey-canvas>

FIGURE 9. THE USER JOURNEY CANVAS TEMPLATE

Therefore, aligning the OpenAIRE-Nexus dissemination and communication channels with the Users’ Journey path and actions is important to ensure the best user satisfaction and engagement³⁶.

In the following subsection, the Users’ Journey is presented by using the categorization of similar user actions. For example, the OpenAIRE-Nexus services that use a dashboard for their users to manage and configure the information they select (PROVIDE, CONNECT, MONITOR), are presented together as one journey.

2.3.1.1 THE OPENAIRE RESEARCH GRAPH USER JOURNEY CANVAS

³⁶ <https://canvanizer.com/new/customer-journey-canvas>

FIGURE 10. THE OPENAIRE RESEARCH GRAPH USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.2 THE PROVIDE/CONNECT/MONITOR USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 11. THE OPENAIRE PROVIDE/CONNECT/MONITOR USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.3 THE ARGOS/AMNESIA/ZENODO/EPISCIENCES USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 12. THE OPENAIRE ARGOS/AMNESIA/ZENODO/EPISCIENCES USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.4 THE OPENAIRE EXPLORE USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 13. THE OPENAIRE EXPLORE USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.5 THE OPENAIRE SCHOLEXPLORER/OPENCITATIONS USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 14. THE OPENAIRE SCHOLEXPLORER/OPENCITATIONS USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.6 THE OPENAPC/OPENAIRE USAGECOUNTS/OPENAIRE OPEN SCIENCE OBSERVATORY USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 15. THE OPENAPC/OPENAIRE USAGECOUNTS/OPEN SCIENCE OBSERVATORY USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.3.1.7 THE OPENAIRE AAI USER JOURNEY CANVAS

FIGURE 16. THE OPENAIRE AAI USER JOURNEY CANVAS

2.4 Qualitative

OpenAIRE-Nexus uses qualitative methods for its communication and services dissemination. This is performed in a more user-centric approach:

1. Random interviews with user testers to collect feedback and improve the OpenAIRE-Nexus services
2. Improvements of the overall presentation of the services' websites (UI/UX), colors selected, graphical design, sentiments produced
3. Listening to personal user experiences
4. Communication with previous, via OpenAIRE-Advance project, SMEs that created value-added tools and services for OpenAIRE ecosystem

5. Improvements of visualizations, texts

Some of the future planned actions are:

- Simulation scenarios running on Open Science Corner (in design)
- Podcasts to approach Open Science and OpenAIRE-Nexus in a more human interactive way, describing stories and listening to users’ experiences
- Videos to introduce the OpenAIRE-Nexus services one by one
- Marketing material for all OpenAIRE-Nexus services (example: Leaflets)
- Major redesign of the OpenAIRE catalogue
- Enhancements of OpenAIRE-Nexus services pages

2.4.1 Collaborations with EOSC and INFRAEOSC-07 projects

Furthermore, the OpenAIRE-Nexus communication, support and training team is in close collaboration with the INFRAEOSC-07 and EOSC Future projects, and with stakeholders (i.e. CONNECT Gateways Communities projects) that use and communicate the services. A collaboration in the form of a MOU Agreement is almost ready to be signed with EOSC Future, including action points and dissemination and outreach.

TABLE 10. EOSC FUTURE AND INFRAEOSC-07

EOSC Future will collaborate closely with the INFRAEOSC-07 projects and integrate their outputs in a number of activities including architecture and technical interoperability guidelines, service provisioning, resource provisioning, requirements gathering and analysis, stakeholder engagement and communications, and user support and training.

More specifically, as noted on the EOSC Future DOA, the collaboration between EOSC Future and INFRAEOSC-07 projects is categorized as:

TABLE 11. CATEGORISATION OF COLLABORATION

Stakeholder Engagement and Communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordinate engagement channels with users, user groups, and providers ● Promote services and resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide user and targeted communication channels ● Provide technical expertise to support adoption by users ● Provide materials about services and their technical specifications
User Support and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliver technical support to EOSC service providers to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliver support to long tail of science user communities engaged via the EOSC

	<p>integrate with the EOSC-Core</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver technical support to the Science Projects, other research communities, and SMEs and industry via the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub • Coordinate user support and training across multiple initiatives and providers (including INFRAEOSC-07 projects) • Include in training packages material from horizontal services offered from INFRAEOSC-07 projects • Deliver the EOSC Knowledge Hub 	<p>Portal and research infrastructures and projects engaged via the coordinated calls</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop training materials for horizontal services for the EOSC Knowledge Hub and contribute to coordinated training events
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Finally, the EOSC Secretariat project is also disseminating events, and information related to EOSC and INFRAEOSC-07 projects.

2.4.2 EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (EOSC-DIH)

The OpenAIRE-Nexus services are included in the list of the EOSC services provided to SMEs that will apply to the EOSC DIH pilots calls. An MOU is ready to be signed, and OpenAIRE-Nexus has already presented the services to a group of interested SMEs, where OpenAIRE-Nexus will contribute to promoting the services and EOSC DIH and collaborate with common dissemination activities.

2.5 Quantitative (KPIs)

As described in the DOA, there are predefined quantitative communication KPIs. The list of KPIs are:

TABLE 12. KPIs

Portfolio	Service	#Measure
PUBLISH	Zenodo	#TBsDataTransferred (Unit of access) #ActiveUsers
	Episciences	#Articles (Unit of access) #Journals #Users

	ARGOS	#ProjectsCreated (Unit of access) #DMPtemplates #LanguagesSupported
	Amnesia	#UserVisits #DownloadsOfDesktopTool
MONITOR	MONITOR	#MonitoringGateways (Unit of access) #IndexedRecordsInTheOpenAIREGraph
	UsageCounts	#APIrequests (Unit of access) #RepositoriesRegistered
	Open Citations	#APIrequests (Unit of access) #IndexedRecords #HarvestedDataSources
	Scholexplorer	#APIrequests (Unit of access) #IndexedRecords
	OpenAPC	#DataDeliveringInstitutions (Unit of access) #APIrequests
	Open Science Observatory	#WebVisits
	AAI	#RegisteredUsers (Unit of access) #UsersLogin
DISCOVER	PROVIDE	#Repositories #BrokeringEvents
	EXPLORE	#APIrequests (Unit of Access) #userVisits
	CONNECT	#CommunityGateways (Units of access) #ActiveUsers

2.6 OpenAIRE-Nexus Communication Material

New communication materials for the OpenAIRE-Nexus brand ID were created in alignment with the OpenAIRE logo.

FIGURE 17. *THE LONG VERSION OF THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS LOGO*

FIGURE 18. *THE SHORT VERSION OF THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS LOGO*

FIGURE 19. *THE COLOR CODES OF THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS LOGO*

OpenAIRE-Nexus services already have logos assigned to them, so there was no need to create new ones. However, for the OpenAIRE catalogue, a new logo was created.

FIGURE 20. *THE NEW OPENAIRE CATALOGUE LOGO*

Furthermore, specifically for events and presentations, PowerPoint template images were created, such as the example in Figure 21.

FIGURE 21. OPENAIRE-NEXUS EXAMPLE OF MATERIAL DESIGNED FOR PRESENTATIONS

Lastly, podcasts may be hosted on well-known hosting platforms and/or also promoted on a dedicated page. An example is shown in Figure 21 (Reference: <https://medium.com/alchemyx>).

The screenshot shows the AlchemistX website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Founders, Investors, Corporate Innovators, Our Portfolio, and a highlighted Contact Us button. The main content area features a large blue banner for a podcast episode titled "E.17 - Andi Mann: The Innovation Mix". On the left of the banner is a circular portrait of Andi Mann. To the right, the episode title is displayed in large, bold text. Below the title, it says "Published on August 19, 2021" and provides a short biography of Andi Mann. A progress bar indicates the episode is 1:07:06 long. Below the progress bar are social media sharing icons for various platforms. At the bottom left of the banner, it says "AlchemistX: Innovators Inside".

Recent Episodes

The "Recent Episodes" section displays three episode cards. Each card features a circular portrait of the guest, the episode title, a short quote, and a "Listen now >" link. The first card is for "E.17 - Andi Mann: The Innovation Mix" with a quote: "Having an idea is easy. Getting it done is hard, understanding how to get it done even harder" - Andi Mann. The second card is for "E.16 - Mark Pesce: Next Billion Seconds" with a quote: "Innovators will see the problem and the solution, possibly a full generation ahead of the organization seeing it" - Mark Pesce. The third card is for "E.15 - Mayra Ceja: Ender's Game" with a quote: "In order to create change and really drive Innovation, you have to start with a start-up mindset and be able to move quickly." - Mayra Ceja. Below the episode cards is a yellow button labeled "All Episodes".

FIGURE 22. AN EXAMPLE OF A WEBSITE FOR PODCASTS

3 THE VALUE PROPOSITIONS OF THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS SERVICE PORTFOLIOS

The OpenAIRE Nexus portfolio consists of three bundles of services: PUBLISH, MONITOR, and DISCOVER.

OpenAIRE-Nexus Service Portoflio(s)

FIGURE 23. THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS SERVICE PORTFOLIOS

The categorization of the service portfolios (Figure 23) depicts what each bundle offers to users, and what the users can perform. In the next section, the VPC files of all OpenAIRE-Nexus services are drafted by the service managers of each service. Then, a random exchange of VPC files among service managers was rolled out, so that each service manager could review and provide feedback on another VPC service. That process, triggered the service managers to spot something that they could find interesting for their own service VPC and add it in a second round of review, or think as a user of a service and provide feedback to a colleague service manager and add some information or ask to explain better an argument.

3.1 PUBLISH Portfolio

The PUBLISH portfolio consists of the following services: Episciences, Zenodo, Amnesia, and ARGOS. This section presents a detailed VPC for each one of the PUBLISH portfolio services.

3.1.1 Episciences Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 24. THE EPISCIENCES VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.1.2 Zenodo Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 25. THE ZENODO VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.1.3 Amnesia Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 26. THE AMNESIA VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.1.4 ARGOS Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 27. THE ARGOS VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2 MONITOR Portfolio

3.2.1 OpenAIRE Research Graph Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 28. THE OPENAIRE RESEARCH GRAPH VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.2 OpenAIRE MONITOR Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 29. THE OPENAIRE MONITOR VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.3 ScholeXplorer Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 30. THE SCHOLEXPLOER VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.4 OpenCitations Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 31. THE OPENCITATIONS VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.5 OpenAPC Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 32. THE OPENAPC VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.6 UsageCounts Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 33. THE USAGECOUNTS VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.2.7 OpenAIRE AAI Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 34. THE OPENAIRE AAI VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.3 DISCOVER Portfolio

3.3.1 OpenAIRE EXPLORE Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 35. THE OPENAIRE EXPLORE VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.3.2 OpenAIRE CONNECT - Research Community Dashboard Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 36. THE OPENAIRE CONNECT VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

3.3.3 OpenAIRE PROVIDE Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 37. THE OPENAIRE PROVIDE VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

4 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

4.1 Communication goals

The main communication goals of OpenAIRE-Nexus are focused on the services and are presented below.

TABLE 13. COMMUNICATION GOALS

Goal	Measurement
Generate media & related initiatives interest	Monitoring tools, statistics of social media platforms and Matomo analytics

Generate awareness of the portfolio services among current OpenAIRE users	Via social media, call to action on newsletters, informative articles, participation in events, continuous contact with NOADs, and direct outreach with stakeholders
Generate awareness of the portfolio services among EOSC users	Via social media, mentions and interaction with EOSC communication channels, events, calendar invitations, newsletters, EOSC-DIH, collaboration through INFRAEOSC-07 projects
Generate demand based on-demand insights	Via reports, usage of services, KPIs, analytics, user testing and interviews, discussions with selected users.

4.2 Stakeholders of the OpenAIRE-Nexus services

The main categorization of the OpenAIRE-Nexus services is presented in the following table. Over time and as the services evolve, more users can be identified and added.

TABLE 14. *STAKEHOLDERS OF SERVICES*

Stakeholder	Description	Services
Researchers	Researchers in partnering with research communities	Zenodo, Amnesia, Argos, MONITOR, CONNECT, OpenCitations, Scholexplorer, EXPLORE
Research Communities	Research communities that are domain or topic-focused topic (i.e. COVID-19, SDSN, AGINFRA, CLARIN, Elixir Greece)	Zenodo, Amnesia, Argos, MONITOR, CONNECT, Open Science Observatory, UsageCounts, OpenCitations, EXPLORE
Research Infrastructures	Research Infrastructures, ESFRIs and global peers	MONITOR, CONNECT, Zenodo (communities), Amnesia, UsageCounts, EXPLORE
Content providers/ Publishing platforms	Infrastructures and platforms used in content and method publishing and scholarly communication	PROVIDE (Broker, Validator), UsageCounts, EXPLORE
e-Infrastructures, Data Initiatives	Service providers of IT and support/training supporting services for research sharing, processing and publishing in Open Science	Argos, Zenodo, MONITOR, UsageCounts, Open Science Observatory, EXPLORE

Research Performing Organizations, Libraries	Universities or Research Institutes	MONITOR, Argos, OpenCitations, OpenAPC, Episciences, Amnesia, Open Science Observatory, UsageCounts
Local, national and EU policy makers	Decision-makers of governmental and funding agencies that design interventions and fund programmes related to open science and innovation.	MONITOR, Argos, Open Science Observatory
EU and research institution's project officers, national contact points	Administrative staff in support of project management and grant writing/support	Argos, Amnesia, MONITOR, Open Science Observatory
Citizens / public	Citizen scientist groups involved in projects.	Zenodo, Amnesia, EXPLORE
SME's	IT solutions providers and new tech start-ups developing software products, tools & apps for open publishing.	EXPLORE, MONITOR, Amnesia, Open Science Observatory, Argos

It should be noted that, compared to the EOSC ecosystem actors, identified back in 2021 in an official report named “Digital skills for FAIR and open science: Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group”³⁷, OpenAIRE-Nexus has a broader entry for potential stakeholders like SMEs and administrative staff.

³⁷

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/af7f7807-6ce1-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190694287>

FIGURE 38. THE EOSC ECOSYSTEM ACTORS

4.3 Communication and outreach with KPIs

TABLE 15. COMMUNICATION, OUTREACH & KPIs

Communication Actions	KPIs
Branding & communication material, channels	
Develop service portfolios key messages, motto and online & printed identity material	#2-5 hashtags to use for dissemination in social media #1 PPT & #4 document templates (for factsheets, guides, workshops, webinars) #audio & video slogan(s), 1 min video snippets for each service: teasers to illustrate key messages
Develop communication guidelines & good practices for EOSC portfolio services dissemination activities and EOSC brand promotion	Create a document explaining the communication strategy, how to use key messages, how to harmonise talking/presenting, how to use own social media for project dissemination

Produce printed & digital project brochures, flyers, moo cards, posters, how-to guides, perks for events, workshops, design in different shapes and sizes to reveal key messages by service. All will be translated to different languages by OpenAIRE NOADs. Distinct versions for scientific fora (e.g., novel technical approaches) and for EOSC / user community symposia	#500-1,500 portfolio services flyers and/or moo cards At least 8 project posters, At least 2-6 roller banners for events, At least 10 digital project flyers/brochures, banners
Produce audio material, slogan(s), for social media, for podcasts Produce videos for training and demonstration purposes	At least 8 podcasts (up to 60min each) with interviews and discussions about the OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio services. Participation in podcasts held by external actors to further communicate the project objectives, outcomes, EOSC and European Commission research activities (reference to INFRAEOSC-03 projects as well) >14 videos
Create awareness to internal decision makers that can help OpenAIRE-Nexus to achieve implementation, impact & sustainability goals	Use OpenAIRE internal mailing & communication lists Use OpenAIRE, COAR, EOSC mailing lists. Inviting to informational meetings, workshops & events
Campaigns	
Social media campaigns	>10 per year around relevant events One on open data for sustainability & social innovation (OA week)
Campaigns for outreach to all stakeholders, press and media (via newsletters, by using campaigns systems i.e. Mailchimp)	#2 campaigns per year/per service At least #8 press releases per year on stories & outcomes At least #20 news items per year Monthly interviews (community calls) with research community members explaining open science stories & successes in simple language (to disseminate through various channels) Monthly newsletters embedded into the OpenAIRE current campaign strategy
Outreach of policy & decision makers informing about project activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact	One memo per month informing research communities One memo (high level) per semester informing funding agencies (e.g. project officers, unit directors) Monthly memos for NOADs to distribute services to MS Monthly memos for relevant e-Infrastructures to see progress, overlaps and gaps to their services
Scientific outreach	
Publication of scientific papers in journals or conferences	At least #6 publications to journals presenting OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio services, findings At least #4 publications to journals/conferences related to Computer Science and Information Science topics

Organization of special sessions or workshops in scientific conferences	At least 2 special sessions or workshops per year in a highly visible or relevant conference At least 1 special session or workshop per year at relevant IT in social sciences
Preparation of articles in general science communication & publication outlets	At least 4 articles per year at related blogs and websites (i.e. EOSC)
Outreach	
Meetings with stakeholders (content and service providers)	At least #2 per year Online community calls for each service (quarterly for most)
Demonstrations of the <i>OpenAIRE-Nexus</i> recommendations and offers at funders, policy makers-dominated events (e-IRG, ESFRIs)	At least at #6 related events during the project's lifetime
Participation in meetups with interest in OpenAIRE-Nexus services, technologies, and system architecture	At least #2 presentations during the project's duration
Creation and promotion of Open Science Practice Corners for all stakeholders	#1 main dedicated page with practical exercises and how-to, step by step guides for all stakeholders At least #1500 new unique visitors and users
Reach through the OpenAIRE and EOSC communication channels	At least #200 mentions in social media (including buzz indicators) At least #800 potential reach followers, subscribers At least #600 impressions, confirmed views of the new services pages/news/posts/videos At least #1000 unique visitors

4.4 Key messages

The additional value of the VPCs is, as mentioned in its methodology description, the ability to draw key messages of services³⁸ as shown in Figure 36.

³⁸ <https://www.b2binternational.com/research/methods/faq/what-is-the-value-proposition-canvas/>

FIGURE 39. KEY MESSAGES METHODOLOGY BASED ON SERVICES PVCs

More specifically, the combinations of Benefits and Experience of services can be combined to develop the core messages of a service. The features and experience, when combined, can help us identify the areas of improvement.

An example with ARGOS follows below:

TABLE 16. ARGOS KEY MESSAGES EXAMPLE

ARGOS Key messages example
“ARGOS - an online tool to Create, Link & Share Data Management Plans”
“ARGOS - a collaborative workspace for delivering Data Management Plans”

“ARGOS - an open extensible service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance of Data Management Plans.”
“An OPENAIRE service to Create, Link & Share FAIR DMP
“ARGOS - A service for machine actionable data management planning”

4.5 Stakeholders Communication plan

Based on previous sections, after drafting the VPCs, the SWOT and competitive analysis, and stakeholder’s matrix, a stakeholders communication plan can be drafted for each OpenAIRE-Nexus service. An example for ARGOS follows below.

TABLE 17. ARGOS STAKEHOLDERS COMMUNICATION PLAN EXAMPLE

ARGOS Stakeholders communication plan example						
	Stakeholder	Interest	Key Issues	Communication Vehicle	Frequency	Comments
1	OpenAIRE-Nexus , OpenAIRE communication team	High	Research, training, funder satisfaction, promotion of ARGOS, KPIs - branding, growth, market penetration, etc.	Social media, newsletter, media production, users monitoring and growth, media kit, Podcasts	Always on	
2	NOADs	High	National promotion of ARGOS, top-down	Emails, Skype, Newsletters, Podcasts	Moderate	
3	Amnesia	Moderate	Co-promotion of service	Show reference, redirect to ARGOS page	Once	Applies for any related service of OpenAIRE

4	Working group of ARGOS	High	Media kit	Emails	Moderate	Designer, developer, product manager
5	Technical OpenAIRE team	Moderate	Beta testing, Releases, Integrations	Emails, Skype, GitHub	On new development action	
6	Developing team	Moderate	Beta testing, Releases	Skype, emails, GitHub	On new development action	
7	Product Manager	High	Final release, Growth	Boards, Trello, Internal tools, Emails, Skype	Weekly	
8	EOSC	High	Enhancement of Services catalogue	Via account in EOSC, API	Automatically updated	e-Infrastructure
9	Funders	High	ROI, Reputation, Social good, Value	Emails,, personal networks, Pilots, PR	On every new release, per month	Pilots to point on funders goals
10	Policy makers	Low	Reputation, Social good, Value	Emails, mail material, personal networks, Pilots	On every new release, per month	Pilots to point on policy makers goals
11	Research facilitators, NCPs, EU liaison offices	High	Promote Open Science, open-source DMPs, Research in EU, top-down	Emails, mail material, personal networks, Pilots, Podcasts, PR	On every new release, per month	Pilots to point on actors' goals
12	UN	Low	Promote UN Goals and Research with ARGOS	Emails, mail material, Pilots, Demo, Podcasts, Blog, PR	On every new release, per	Pilots to point on UNL goals

					month	
13	EUDAT	High	Data preservation, access, reuse, integration of ARGOS, branding ARGOS	Emails, Skype, Pilots, material, social media references, Webinars	Weekly	e-Infrastructure
14	RDA group on common standards DMP	High	Informative, Workshop, Training	Plenaries, workshops, hackathons, website, newsletter, Demo	Monthly, per quarter, per year	
15	HELIX	High	Data management, preservation, access, reuse, integration of ARGOS	Website support, Demo	Per quarter	Same applies to all national research repositories
16	Copernicus	Low	White label, Data management, preservation, access, reuse, support of ARGOS	Website support, Demo, Newsletters	Monthly	
17	SMEs with R&D i.e. Samsung, Huawei, Pharma's	Moderate	White label ³⁹	Emails, mail material, personal networks, Pilots, PR	On every new release, per Quarter	Pilots need to fit to the SME needs
18	(Scientific) Journals Publishers	High	Keep record of data, preserve, reference	Emails, Pilots, Demos, Newsletters, PR	Monthly	Mostly open science journals
19	Research Communities	High	Knowledge transfer, FAIR principles, training	Workshops, hands-on, videos, Demo, Podcasts, Blog, Lists, Blog	Depends, per new ARGOS version	
20	Press/Media	Low	Informative, Social	Press releases, Blog, Podcasts,	Bi-weekly, moderate	

³⁹ White label needs a dedicated page for the target group

				Demos, Newsletters, Videos		
21	Individuals (Simms et al.)	High	Personal interest, self-usage	Newsletters, Demos, Pilots, Podcasts, Webinars, Workshops, Lists, Meetups, Blog	Bi-weekly	Influencer, his paper initiated the RDA group
22	Tool providers	Moderate	Professional interest, training, workshops, hackathons	GitHub, Newsletter, Lists, Meetups	Weekly/d depends on ARGOS releases	Depends on orgs policies
23	Infrastructure operators	Moderate	Integrations, training, workshops	GitHub, Lists, Emails, Skype, notifications	Always on	
24	Repository staff and managers	High	Enhancements, training, workshops	GitHub, Lists, Emails, notifications	Always on	
25	Software developers	Moderate	Reporting, enhancing, Training, Workshops, Personal interest	GitHub, ref to online web page under support	Always on	
26	Librarians	High	White label, DMP support for data preservation, FAIRness, Support researchers	Emails, material, newsletters, Pilots, Blog, Podcasts	On every new release, per Quarter	
27	W3C	Moderate	Metadata standards in DMP, Training, Workshops	Newsletters, Blog	Per semester	
28	Force 11 FAIR DMP	Moderate	Informative, Support researchers, Support communities	Demos, Workshops, Hands-on, Blog, Podcasts	Per month	DMP Fora in general
29	Belmont Forum e-infrastructures	Moderate	Research funding	Pilots on environmental research	Per 2 months	

30	Volunteers	High	Tool support, growth, integration, promotion, enrichment	Fora, Lists, Meetups	Always on	
31	NGOs	Moderate	White label	Emails, newsletters, maybe Pilots	On every new release, per Quarter	
32	OpenAIRE NaMeCo	High	Research promotion DMP promotion	Networking, Emails, Newsletters	Once per 2 months	NaMeCo is in progress
33	Data stewards/experts	High	Workshops, Training	Demos, Podcasts, Newsletters, Pilots, Blog,	Monthly	

5 ENGAGEMENT PLAN

OpenAIRE-Nexus engagement is in collaboration and close alignment with the main pillars of the project:

- The project Communication
- The Support & Training
- Synergies & Networks
- Measurable actions
- Internal User Funnels

This is depicted in the following figure.

FIGURE 40. THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS COMMUNICATION, ENGAGEMENT, SYNERGIES & NETWORKS INTERCONNECTIONS

5.1 Strategy to engage with EOSC users

OpenAIRE Nexus is part of the EOSC MarketPlace where EOSC users can be directed to OpenAIRE services by browsing by Scientific Domain or Categories in Figure 41.

FIGURE 41. *The EOSC MARKETPLACE CATEGORIES OF SERVICES*

The categories of services that can be browsed by EOSC marketplace’s users are multiple. They allow easy access to the catalogue offered by the services providers.

The engagement strategy is focused on the creation of users’ habits: by using the EOSC marketplace as a gateway to research infrastructures, tools for data aggregators and integrators, instruments to process and analyse data, databases and tools related with security and operations of data sharing, and the training materials on Open Science. The ‘users’ habit’ envisioned consists in consulting the EOSC portal whenever the user needs tools, instruments, infrastructures or training material related with Open Science.

A survey to improve the user experience is currently ongoing and we expect to better engage the internal stakeholders and external users. Improvements by virtual tour are ongoing as well as front and back-end changes designed for users’ needs.

We will study user behavior towards EOSC access to our catalogues and services with interviews, performing habit testing, what triggers the user curiosity towards the EOSC catalogues, and identifying users’ ambassadors to spread the word, and the consultation of the EOSC marketplace. Based on media statistics, surveys and interviews, we will focus on better categorisation to direct the interest towards the OpenAIRE Nexus services.

5.2 The National Open Access Desks (NOADs)

Major engagement actors of OpenAIRE are the NOADs network. It is formed, supported and developed by OpenAIRE. The NOADs network is composed of experts and supporters of Open Science in Europe, located in every European country, and usually in university libraries. It is an active force to develop Open Science practices, services and policies at a national level. When organisations, universities, libraries, research communities, policy makers, researchers, and more national organisations require information on Open Science, and send inquiries about OpenAIRE services, the NOADs are the representatives of OpenAIRE in their countries and organise events, presentations, workshops, initiate discussions and match the users needs with OpenAIRE services. They are the engaging experts, the national facilitators of Open Science developments. A dedicated web page⁴⁰ that presents all the NOADs per country is available on the OpenAIRE portal.

The engagement strategy of OpenAIRE-Nexus is built around NOADs network as the enablers of vertical knowledge exchange from outside of OpenAIRE to the inside of it, and the experts who mobilise community ties. Briefly, NOADs:

- Leverage national knowledge and outreach to research communities and beyond
- Empower national actors on Open Science to develop necessary capacities at local and national level to achieve Open Science and policy alignment
- Put forward and assist national decision makers to position Open Access and Open Science into national agendas
- Foster and support through Open Science practices the adoption of OpenAIRE-Nexus services
- Cooperate with national research infrastructure nodes to build connections among research communities and OpenAIRE-Nexus services
- Create a feedback loop process among local and national actors regarding the OpenAIRE-Services adoption and usage
- Expand the OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolio services brand and European Open Science to the global Open Science network

6 RISK ANALYSIS

There are a few implementation risks when it comes to applying the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy. There is always the risk of technical delays that may affect the communication of a service and a portfolio.

Apart from that, there is a chance that the budget allocated under Virtual Access for services, does not match with expectations (lower or higher) and may affect the re-distribution of effort,

⁴⁰ <https://www.openaire.eu/contact-noads>

communication process, level of communication, timing, and expansion of dissemination activities. Furthermore, as noted in WP4, WP5 and WP6, it is important to track and measure the units of access for each service and adjust the communication efforts to the services that need more support and dissemination.

Another issue that may arise, is the EOSC interoperability delivery of the portfolio of services that may expose the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy. In that case, the communication strategy will be adapted into a more generic approach and then refocus back on interoperability and integrations of portfolio services. OpenAIRE-Nexus is in direct communication with the INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 projects and any adjustments will be aligned.

The Covid-19 crisis is an external factor to the initial planning of events and conferences via live participation. Any accompanied printed material, banners and perks are postponed for now. Participation in virtual events and conferences can continue without issues, while face-to-face meetings with users, to discuss in a more open and friendly way about the services, receive feedback and engage them cannot currently be done. These will be achieved by virtual means, digital forms, and questionnaires.

7 SUMMARY

Figure 42 illustrates the connections among the tools, methodologies and communication means used to successfully understand and combine information from OpenAIRE-Nexus users. After the analysis of that information, the communication and engagement strategies can be drawn up, and be re-evaluated every year, along with the qualitative measures (i.e. KPIs). It can be called the OpenAIRE-Nexus pillars – Services, Communication, Engagement.

FIGURE 42. THE OPENAIRE-NEXUS PILLARS

We also need to consider that since the approach is more user-centric, any user characteristics, needs, reactions, might change over time. The approaches and methodologies of the VPC, S.M.A.R.T. Marketing, and Customer Journey Canvas are allowing service managers, in close collaboration with the communication and engagement team of OpenAIRE AMKE, to easily update and align any external demand with what the OpenAIRE-Nexus services offer.

It is important to mention that all OpenAIRE-Nexus communication activities are in close collaboration with the technical team and the overall roadmap of the OpenAIRE-Nexus portfolios interoperability with EOSC, as described in deliverables D3.1 and D3.2. Additionally, for detailed information on Support and Training activities planned, the D2.2 is highly recommended.